

A SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH TO IDENTIFYING ONLINE FAKE NEWS

Amadi Chizoba Bright

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Fake news refers to intentionally and verifiably false stories that are largely disseminated through social media networks or the internet. Such news can be very persuasive, which makes it necessary to develop strategies to identify and critically assess news read and circulated on social media. This paper presents a model to detect online fake news using supervised machine learning algorithms. In this paper a fake_or_real_news dataset was used in feeding and training the machine learning algorithms. This dataset was preprocessed and extract using feature extraction. The dataset which have 4 columns originally was further divided into two columns which are the text and label columns. The label Columns was further processed to be a REAL column. In this paper we used three supervised machine learning algorithms in training our model. The three algorithms are as LogisticRegression, Support Vector Classifier, MultinomialNB. After training and evaluating the performance of the three models, the results shows that Logistic Regression had an accuracy of about 91.9%, Support Vector Classifier had an accuracy of about 86.8% and MultinomialNB had an accuracy result of 88.5%. Therefore, this paper recommends the use of Logistic Regression in detecting online fake news.

1. Introduction

Fake news in Nigeria has cause a lot of damages especially in political era, spreading false information across the internet in other to make critics, cause religious and ethnic division, damage reputations as well as drawing more persons to the website. Some persons do spread fake information on their websites in other to get more persons visiting their website. Fake news refers to intentionally and verifiably false stories that are largely disseminated through social media networks. It can be very persuasive and therefore makes it necessary to develop strategies to identify and critically assess news read and circulated on social media. False news reached more people than the truth; the top 1% of false news cascades diffuse to between 1000 and 100,000 people, whereas the truth rarely diffuse to more than 1000 people. Falsehood also diffuses faster than the truth. The relevance of fake news has increased in post-truth politics. For media outlets, the ability to attract viewers to their websites is necessary to generate online advertising revenue; publishing a story with false content that attracts user's benefits advertisers and improves ratings. Fake news has recently raised a lot of concerns because of its prevalent impact. The problem is not only unique to online environments; it is also present in the conventional media. The internet has enabled a whole new way to publish, share and consume information and news with very little regulation or editorial standards. Many people now get news from social media sites and networks and

often it can be difficult to tell if stories are credible or not. Information overload and a general lack of understanding about how the internet works, has also contributed to an increase in fake news or hoax stories. Social media sites can play a big part in increasing the reach of these types of stories.

The proliferation of Fake News on social media has been a source of widespread concern. One of the main approaches to automatically detect this type of news is based on crowd signals, i.e., opinions manifested by social media users concerning whether the news are fake or not. Although promising, this approach depends on information that is not always available: the explicit opinion of the users about the news to be checked [1]. During natural disasters or crises, users on social media tend to easily believe contents of postings related to the events, and retweet the postings with hope them of reaching to many other users. Unfortunately, there are malicious users who understand the tendency and post misinformation such as spam and fake messages with expectation of wider propagation [2]. This paper provides a model for detecting online fake news using supervised machine learning algorithms.

2. Related Work

The paper “Fake and spam messages detecting misinformation during natural disasters on social media” conducted a case study of 2013 Moore Tornado and Hurricane Sandy [2]. Concretely, they understand behaviors of these malicious users, analyze properties of spam, fake and legitimate messages, proposed flat and hierarchical classification approaches, and detect both fake and spam messages with the ability to distinguish between them. Their experimental results show that their proposed approaches identify spam and fake messages with 96.43% accuracy and 0.961 F-measure.

The paper “The spread of true and false news online” investigated the differential diffusion of all of the verified true and false news stories distributed on Twitter from 2006 to 2017 [3]. The data they used comprises of 126,000 stories tweeted by 3 million people more than 4.5 million times. They classified news as true or false using information from six independent fact-checking organizations that exhibited 95 to 98% agreement on the classifications. They also found that false news was more novel than true news, which they suggest that people were more likely to share novel information. It was also reveal in the study that robots accelerated the spread of true and false news at the same rate, implying that false news spreads more than the truth because humans, not robots, are more likely to spread it.

The paper “Automatically Identifying Fake News in Popular Twitter Threads” presented by [4] developed a method for automating fake news detection on Twitter by learning to predict accuracy assessments in two credibility-focused Twitter datasets: CREDBANK, a crowdsourced dataset of accuracy assessments for events in Twitter and PHEME, a dataset of potential rumors in Twitter and journalistic assessments of their accuracies. They applied this method to Twitter content sourced from Buzz Feed’s fake news dataset and show models trained against crowdsourced workers outperform models based on journalists’ assessment and models trained on a pooled dataset of both crowdsourced workers and journalists. All three datasets, was aligned into a uniform format. They use a feature analysis in identifying features that are most predictive for crowdsourced and journalistic accuracy assessments, results of which are consistent with

prior work. The paper, concluded with a discussion contrasting accuracy and credibility and why models of non-experts outperform models of journalists for fake news detection in Twitter.

The paper “Fake news detection on social media: A data mining perspective” presented a comprehensive review of detecting fake news on social media, including fake news characterization on psychology and social theories, existing algorithms from a data mining perspective, evaluation metrics and representative datasets [5].

The paper “Fake news detection on social media via implicit crowd signals” proposed a crowd signal-based method that does not demand the users’ explicit opinion to detect fake news [1].

The proposed method infers the users’ opinion from their news spreading (publication/propagation) behaviour. Preliminary experiments carried out with two real-world datasets provided evidence that the proposed method can detect fake news without demanding the explicit opinion of users about the news and without compromising the classification results obtained by the state-of-the-art crowd signal-based method.

3. Design methodology

Figure 1: Architecture of the proposed system

This system uses a dataset called `fake_or_real_news`. The dataset was downloaded from `kaggle.com` with 4 columns which are unnamed, title, text and label. The dataset was preprocessed to be text and label. The text column contains both real and fake news information while the label column shows if the news is real or fake. The label column was also preprocessed to be either 1 or 0, where 1 represents that news is real and 0 represents that the news is fake. The new dataset (text, label) was split into x variable and y variable, where x holds the text column and y holds the label column. The x variable was parsed to remove words, called tokenization, this words need to be encoded as integers or floating point values for use as input in training a machine learning algorithm. This whole process is called feature extraction which we used `CountVectorizer` in achieving it. The dataset was trained using 3 machine learning algorithms which are `MultinomialNB` from `Naïve_Bayes`, `Support Vector Classifier` and `Logistic Regression`. We used these three models in making predictions and scoring their accuracy.

Unnamed: 0		title	text	label
0	8476	You Can Smell Hillary's Fear	Daniel Greenfield, a Shillman Journalism Fello...	FAKE
1	10294	Watch The Exact Moment Paul Ryan Committed Pol...	Google Pinterest Digg Linkedin Reddit Stumbleu...	FAKE
2	3608	Kerry to go to Paris in gesture of sympathy	U.S. Secretary of State John F. Kerry said Mon...	REAL
3	10142	Bernie supporters on Twitter erupt in anger ag...	— Kaydee King (@KaydeeKing) November 9, 2016 T...	FAKE
4	875	The Battle of New York: Why This Primary Matters	It's primary day in New York and front-runners...	REAL

Figure 2: showing original dataset downloaded from kaggle.com created by Raluca Chitic

4. Result and discussion

In this paper, a machine learning model was trained to detect if a news is real or fake. This model uses fake_or_real_news dataset which have 4 columns but was preprocessed to a dataset with two columns (text, label). This new dataset was divided into x and y variable where x variable holds both fake and real news. The x variable was fit transformed using CountVectorizer class which was gotten from feature extraction. The variable x and y were further divided into x_train, x_test, y_train and y_test. This x_train and y_train were being fitted or trained using four machine algorithms which are LogisticRegression, Support Vector Classifier and MultinomialNB from Naïve_Bayes. These 3 algorithms were tested and scored based on accuracy, LogisticRegression had an accuracy of about 91.9%, Support Vector Classifier had an accuracy of about 86.8% and MultinomialNB had an accuracy of about 88.5%. The model highest accuracy is the Logistic Regression which was saved and used in detection of fake news and real news.

	text	REAL
0	Daniel Greenfield, a Shillman Journalism Fello...	0
1	Google Pinterest Digg Linkedin Reddit Stumbleu...	0
2	U.S. Secretary of State John F. Kerry said Mon...	1
3	— Kaydee King (@KaydeeKing) November 9, 2016 T...	0
4	It's primary day in New York and front-runners...	1

Figure 3: showing Training data which was been used in feeding the 3 machine learning algorithms

Figure 4: showing the histogram of the entire dataset

Figure 5: showing correlation matrix of the dataset

Figure 6: Showing a Count plot of real and fake news

Figure 7: showing a histogram of real and fake news

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.82	0.94	0.87	1066
1	0.92	0.78	0.85	1025
accuracy			0.86	2091
macro avg	0.87	0.86	0.86	2091
weighted avg	0.87	0.86	0.86	2091

Figure 8: showing a classification report of support vector classifier

Figure 9: showing error rate vs support vector classifier

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.92	0.92	0.92	1066
1	0.92	0.92	0.92	1025
accuracy			0.92	2091
macro avg	0.92	0.92	0.92	2091
weighted avg	0.92	0.92	0.92	2091

Figure 10 showing classification report on Logistic Regression algorithm

Figure 11 showing error rate vs Logistic Regression

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.92	0.85	0.88	1066
1	0.85	0.93	0.89	1025
accuracy			0.89	2091
macro avg	0.89	0.89	0.89	2091
weighted avg	0.89	0.89	0.89	2091

Figure 12 showing classification report of MultinomialNB classifier

Figure 13 showing error rate vs MultinomialNB classifier

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In this paper three machine learning algorithms were used to train and analyse the model. A dataset which contains both real and fake news information was used in feeding and training the model. After testing for accuracy, LogisticRegression had the highest accuracy which is approximately 91.9%, while MultinomialNB had approximately 88.5% accuracy and Support Vector Classifier had 86.8% accuracy. Logistic Regression was saved and tested in detecting fake news; thus presenting the model with a better performance in detecting fake news. This paper can further be extended by using convolution neural network in training to take both pictures and text in feeding the network. It can also be extended into a real system by using it as a chrome browser extension.

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